

Michael and Ring Expansion Reactions of Ethyl Camphor Carboxylate

MOHAMED SALAH EL-HOSSINI

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Mansoura University, Damietta, Egypt

Manuscript received 10 April 1990, accepted 3 July 1990

Ethyl camphor carboxylate (prepared from sodium hydrazide and diethyl carbonate) was reacted with dimethylacetylenedicarboxylate. Ring expansion occurred to give the substituted-cyclooctanone (2). Michael reactions of the title compound 1 with unsaturated ketones gave adducts, some of which under went further transformations.

CAMPHOR has been used as a mild expectorant and to relieve griping. Applied externally, camphor acts as a rubefacient and mild analgesic and employed in liniments, as a counter irritant in fibrositis, neuralgia and similar conditions¹.

It has been reported recently²⁻⁴ that the Michael adduct from dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate and 4-carboethoxy-1-benzoazepin-5-one or 2-carboethoxy-6-methoxytetralone-1 undergoes ring expansion simultaneously to give 1-benzoazoninone and benzocyclooctenone derivatives respectively. This prompted us to investigate the behaviour of the title compound in such reactions to produce compounds which are expected to have potential biological activity.

The formation of ethyl camphor carboxylate (1) from camphor using sodium hydride and diethyl carbonate proved to be more successful than the method originally claimed¹ both in terms of purity and yield. Distillation (130°/0.04 mm Hg) of the brown liquid product allowed the isolation of sufficient quantities of pure material of the β -keto-ester required to investigate this proposal.

The reaction between DMAD and sodium salt of ethyl camphor carboxylate afforded a brown oil. Tlc indicated that this oil contained three components. Chromatography (chloroform as eluent) allowed the separation of the major product which was identified as the two carbon ring expanded product 2. The initial identification of the structure was based chiefly on nmr evidence which demonstrated that the product possessed a highly enolic proton and lacked any vinylic protons ruling out the possibility of the Michael adduct 3.

The proposed mechanism may be formulated as proceeding through initial Michael addition of the β -keto-ester carbanion to the acetylene. The resultant Michael adduct anion (4) undergoes intramolecular cyclisation, by attack on the carbonyl carbon, to give the cyclobutene intermediate (5). Subsequent ring opening, isomerisation of the double bond and protonation would yield the highly enolic triester 2.

Michael reaction of 1 with benzylidene-acetone was performed with the expectation that the cyclic product 7 would be formed via intramolecular cyclisation of the Michael adduct. However, the reaction led to 6 as the only product and no cyclised product was isolated.

The Michael reaction of 1 with dibenzylidene-acetone afforded 8. The identification followed from analytical and spectral data, which showed that only the mono adduct 8 was formed. Further support for structure 8 was obtained from its reaction with *p*-thiocresol to give the *p*-tolylthioethyl derivative (9). Reaction of 8 and cyclohexanone gave compound 10 as the final product through intramolecular condensation of the aldol-crotonic type^{5,6}.

(1)

(2)

(3)

(4)

(5)

(6)

(7)

(8)

(9)

(10)

The structures of both 9 and 10 were confirmed from their correct elemental analyses and positive sulphur test for compound 9.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were taken on an Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R 32 spectrometer (90 MHz). Elementary analyses (C, H) of compounds 1, 2, 6 and 8 were found satisfactory.

2-Carboethoxy-3-oxo-4,7,7-trimethylbicyclo[2,2,1]heptane (1): To a stirred suspension of sodium hydride (50% in oil; 4.8 g, 1 mol) in anhydrous toluene (30 cm^3) under nitrogen was added diethyl carbonate (17.7 g, 1.5 mol) followed by dropwise addition of a solution of camphor (7.6 g, 0.5 mol) in toluene. The reaction mixture was then heated (80°) for 6 h, during which it became solid and stirring was terminated. Glacial acetic acid followed by ice-water/2 M hydrochloric acid were then added and the organic layer was separated. Drying and evaporation under reduced pressure afforded a brown liquid, which on distillation (kergel/rohr) yielded a reddish liquid (7.9 g, 70%), (Found: C, 69.21; H, 80.47. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 69.64; H, 8.92%); ν_{max} 1730 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ ester) and 1670 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$).

2-Carboethoxy-3,4-dicarbomethoxy-5-hydroxy-6,9,9-trimethylbicyclo[4,2,1]nonane (2): To sodium hydride (50% dispersion in oil; 2.4 g, 0.05 mol) in dry toluene (35 cm^3) under nitrogen, compound 1 (7.4 g,

0.03 mol) was added with stirring over 0.5 h. The white paste so obtained was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and then cooled to 0° . While stirring, dimethylacetylene dicarboxylate (5 g, 9.03 mol) was added during 1 h keeping the temperature of the reaction mixture below 10° . The reaction was complete after 5 h (shown by tlc). The reaction mixture was cooled, then acetic acid (5 cm^3) and hydrochloric acid (2 M; 10 cm^3) were added, and the separated aqueous layer was washed with toluene ($3 \times 10\text{ cm}^3$). The organic phase was washed with water (10 cm^3), dried and evaporated under reduced pressure to give dark brown oil. Tlc indicated that the oil had three components. Chromatography (CHCl_3) allowed the separation of the major component as a red oil (5.2 g, 44.8%) (Found: C, 60.87; H, 7.21. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_7$ requires: C, 61.95; H, 7.60%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1720 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$, ester), 1680 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ at C-5) and 1580 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$); δ 13.1 (1H, s, exch., OH), 4.0 (9.2H, OCH_2Me), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.5 (3H, s, OCH_3) and 3.6–2.3 (4H, m, CH_2).

2-Carboethoxy-2-[3-oxo-1-phenylbutanyl]-3-oxo-4,7,7-trimethylbicyclo[2,2,1]heptane (6): To a solution of 1 (0.01 mol) in methanol (30 cm^3) containing potassium methoxide (0.01 mol), benzylidene acetone (0.01 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h, left to stand overnight and poured into ice-cold dilute acetic acid (20%). The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (62%), m.p. 92° (Found: C, 73.25; H, 7.12. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 74.79; H, 7.85%).

2-Carboethoxy-2-[3-oxo-1,5-diphenyl-4-pentenyl]-3-oxo-4,7,7-trimethylbicyclo[2,2,1]heptane (8): It was synthesised similarly as above from 1 except that dibenzylidene acetone (0.01 mol) was used, (55%), m.p. 105° (Found: C, 77.81; H, 6.91. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 78.60; H, 7.42%).

2-Carboethoxy-2-[3-oxo-5-(p-tolylthio)ethyl]-1,5-diphenylpentyl]-3-oxo-4,7,7-trimethylbicyclo[2,2,1]heptane (9): A mixture of 8 (0.01 mol) and *p*-thiocresol (0.01 mol) in methanol (40 ml) containing potassium methoxide (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 h. After standing overnight, the product was isolated as described for 6. The resulting compound was crystallised from ethanol as brown solid (70%), m.p. 110° (Found: C, 77.31; H, 6.92. $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires: C, 77.28, H, 7.21%).

2-Carboethoxy-2-[(2,3,4,4a,5,6,7,8-octahydro-2-oxo-4-phenyl-1-naphthyl)benzyl]-3-oxo-4,7,7-trimethylbicyclo[2,2,1]heptane (10): The same procedure as described for 9 was followed except cyclohexanone (0.01 mol) was used as a Michael donor instead of *p*-thiocresol, (60%), m.p. 135° (Found: C, 79.23; H, 7.23. $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 80.29; H, 7.80%).

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to express his sincere gratitude to Dr. G. R. Proctor, Strathclyde University, Glasgow, Scotland, for his guidance and encouragement.

References

1. G. T. WALKER *Mfg. Chem.* 1968 **39** 41.
2. A. J. FREW and G. R. PROCTOR *J. Chem.-Soc. Perkin Trans. 1* 1980 1245.
3. A. J. FREW, G. R. PROCTOR and J. A. SILVERTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1980 1251.
4. M. LENNON, A. MCLEAN, I. MCWATT and G. R. PROCTOR, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1974, 1828.
5. H. STOBBER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1912, **86**, 209, 218.
6. C. F. ALLEN and H. R. SALLANS, *Can. J. Res.*, 1933, **9**, 574.